

Polarographic Behaviour of 2-Mercaptoethanol at the D. M. E.

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The polarographic behaviour of 2-mercaptoethanol ($\text{OH}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SH}$) has been studied at ionic strength 0.1 M NaClO_4 in the pH range (1.42-11.20) at the d.m.e. The electrode process is reversible, diffusion controlled and involves one electron transfer process in the above pH-range. The effects of various supporting electrolytes viz., NaClO_4 , Li_2SO_4 , KCl , KNO_3 and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N Br}$; buffers viz., Britton-Robinson, Clark and Lube's, Michaelis-Borate, $\text{NH}_3\text{-NH}_4\text{Cl}$, acetate and unbuffered media and different solvents such as methanol, ethanol, iso-butanol, acetonitrile, dimethylsulfoxide and dimethyl formamide have also been studied. The dissociation constant of the -SH group is found to be 9.50. Controlled potential electrolysis, interaction with mercuric chloride and mathematical analysis reveal the depolarisation of mercury with the formation of a Hg(I) complex, mercurous mercaptide (RSHg), which rapidly changes to more stable (2:1) mercuric complex (RS_2Hg).

SAXENA *et al.*¹⁻² have investigated the electrochemical behaviour of several mercapto compounds and their metal complexes which have found important application in biological, pharmaceutical and in resin industries. The present communication describes the polarographic behaviour of 2-mercaptoethanol in various supporting electrolytes viz., NaClO_4 , Li_2SO_4 , KCl , KNO_3 and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N Br}$; buffers viz., Britton-Robinson, Clark and Lube's, Michaelis-Borate, acetate and unbuffered media and different solvents such as methanol, ethanol, iso-butanol, acetonitrile, DMF and DMSO for which there is no reference in the literature.

Experimental

2-Mercaptoethanol (referred to herein as RSH) and all other chemicals used were of anal-R (B.D.H.) quality. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation. A manual polarograph and Cambridge pH-meter were used for recording the polarograms and measuring

pH, respectively. The capillary had the following characteristics in 0.1 M NaClO_4 , 0.002% Triton-X-100 (pH 4-80) at 0.10 V vs S.C.E. with h_{eff} value of 50.75 cm , $m = 1.24\text{ mg/sec}$, $t = 5.00\text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 1.594\text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{ sec}^{-1}$. Polarograms were recorded in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen at $(20 \pm 0.1)^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH, buffer constituents and ethanol concentration :

Polarograms of 1.0 mM RSH in 0.1 M NaClO_4 using 0.002% Triton-X-100 as maximum suppressor were recorded at different pH values in Clark and Lube's buffer. An anodic wave was obtained at all pH values (1.42-11.20) [Fig. 1]. The slopes of linear plots of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log(i_d - i)/i$ showed that the electrode reaction was reversible involving one electron transfer process. The values of $E_{1/2}$ shift towards more negative potential with increase in pH [Table 2]. (The point of intersection of the

Fig. 1. Anodic wave of 2-mercaptoethanol at different pH-values.

plots of E_1 vs pH , corresponds to the dissociation constant (pK) of the sulphhydryl group³ and is found to be 9.50 (Table 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ETHANOL CONCENTRATION AT 20°C

Composition (water-alcohol) percentage	Diffusion current Constant (I)	Viscosity (Cp) (Incentipoise)
0.0	1.976	1.000
10	1.693	1.275
20	1.505	1.816
30	1.411	2.323
40	1.349	2.586
50	1.317	2.610
60	1.349	2.470

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON E_1

pH	$E_1(V)$
1.42	0.0600
2.30	0.1000
2.96	0.1400
3.88	0.1950
4.76	0.2490
6.83	0.3765
8.66	0.4825
9.21	0.5112
10.33	0.5341
10.62	0.5352
11.20	0.5370

The nature of the wave remains unchanged in various buffers such as Britton-Robinson, Clark and Lube's, Michaelis-Borate, NH_3-NH_4Cl and acetate. In unbuffered media, an irreversible anodic wave was observed, this may be attributed to the change in pH due to the discharge of H^+ during the oxidation of RSH at the electrode surface⁴.

i_d (total height of the wave i.e., diffusion current) was found to decrease with increase in ethanol concentration upto 50% beyond which it was found to increase. This may be ascribed to the change in viscosity of the solution with change in ratio of the ethanol and water⁵ [Table 1].

Effect of [RSH], Hg-pressure and temperature: i_d changes linearly with [RSH] and mean value of I (diffusion current constant) was found to be 1.985. For 1.0 mM RSH i_d/h_{eff}^2 (0.434 $\mu A cm^{-2}$), temperature-coefficient of i_d 2.036% per degree were almost constant, indicating diffusion controlled nature of the wave.

Effects of various supporting electrolytes and solvents: i_d was measured at pH 4.80 using several supporting electrolytes and solvents. The values of diffusion current constant (I) were found to be in the following order:

$(C_2H_5)_4NBr > KNO_3 > KCl > NaClO_4 \approx Li_2SO_4$
and
acetonitrile > methanol > DMF > ethanol > DMSO > iso-butanol.

This may be due to variation in viscosity of solution⁵ ($I \propto 1/\text{viscosity}$).

Mechanism of the anodic reaction: Since the anodic wave produced by RSH is due to a reversible, diffusion controlled process, it is possible to get an indication of the mechanism of the anodic reaction. If the reaction is the oxidation of RSH to disulphide (RSSR) and the reaction is reversible,

then the potential at every point on the wave should be given by

$$E = \text{const.} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+]_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{[RSSR]_0}{[RSH]_0^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

which can be written

$$E = \text{const.} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [H^+]_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{i}{(i_d - i)^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

At constant pH and at 20°,

$$E = \text{const.}' - \frac{0.059}{2} \log \frac{(i_d - i)^2}{i} \quad \dots (4)$$

The other possible mechanism is the oxidation of RSH with intermediate formation of a free radical and the anodic dissolution of mercury, resulting in the formation of mercury-RSH complex,

Both (5) and (7) involve a one electron transfer process and the potential at any point on the wave is

$$E = E_1 - 0.059 \log \frac{i_d - i}{i} \quad \dots (8)$$

The plot of E vs $\log (i_d - i)/i$ gives a straight line with a slope (0.061 ± 0.003) , close to the theoretical⁷ slope 0.059 (for one electron transfer) to allow the conclusion that (8) represents the electrode reaction. Furthermore it was found that the half-wave potentials were independent of RSH concentrations: this constancy of E_1 is characteristic of (8) but not of (4). The analysis indicates that the anodic reaction of RSH at the d.m.e. occurs either according to (5) and (6) or by the formation of the mercury-RSH compound, (7).

5.0 ml solution of RSH (1.0 mM), in 0.1M $NaClO_4$ at 0.10V (pH 4.80) was electrolysed in nitrogen atmosphere for six hours. Electrolysed solution was then polarographed under identical conditions: a cathodic wave obtained, which corresponded to a reversible⁸ one electron reduction process. On passing H_2S through the electrolysed solution, a black turbidity was noted, showing the presence of soluble mercury in the solution. On the basis of

these observations, the reaction mechanism indicated by (4), (5) and (6) can be discarded. From the evidence we conclude that the product of the anodic reaction of RSH at the d.m.e. is a mercury compound of RSH.

With a view to obtaining more conclusive evidence, solutions containing (I), 1.0 mM RSH, (II) 1.0 mM RSH : 0.25 mM HgCl₂ (III), 1.0 mM RSH : 0.50 mM HgCl₂ were polarographed under identical conditions. Solution (III) yielded a well defined cathodic wave corresponding to one electron reduction having $E_{1/2}$ similar to that of anodic wave of solution (I). [Fig. 2,

1- 1m M RSH : 0.0m M HgCl₂
2- 1m M RSH : 0.25m M HgCl₂
3- 1m M RSH : 0.50m M HgCl₂

Fig. 2. Comparative anodic-cathodic curves of RSH and mercury-RSH compounds.

curve-3 and 1], and solution (II) produced a composite wave, curve 2. These observations clearly indicate that the anodic reaction is solely due to the anodic dissolution of Hg forming its compound with RSH.

The curve for solution (II) showed large diffusion current at zero applied potential, but the same value

of slope and $E_{1/2}$ as that given by solution (III), hence indicating the reduction of same compound mercurous mercaptide (RSHg) and the presence of free mercuric-ions⁹. These observations clearly reveal that the stable species of mercury and RSH is (RS)₂Hg and the cathodic wave given by complex is due to the reduction of RSHg, an unstable compound. Moreover, the diffusion current constant of the complex was 3.39 as compared to 1.95 of RSH, indicating corresponding changes of $D^{1/2}$ values and consequently the size of reducing species. From diffusion current data¹⁰, (taking Tl⁺¹ as a reference substance) n has been determined 0.89 \approx 1 and hence the anodic wave of RSH represents one electron transfer process.

We may conclude that RSH is not oxidised to RSSR at the d.m.e. but it depolarizes the Hg with the formation of unstable RSHg. The reduction wave of (RS)₂Hg corresponds to the reduction of a univalent cation. Hence, the reduction can be best represented by

Apparently (10) is very rapid, hence RSHg is reduced. Stricks and Kolthoff¹¹ have found a similar reaction with reduced glutathione.

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